

JOB SATISFACTION OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Dr. A. C. Lal Kumar

Assistant Professor, G.E.T College of Education, Gudiyattam, Vellore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. A. C. Lal Kumar, "Job Satisfaction of Higher Secondary School Teachers", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Page Number 62-65, Volume 1, Issue 1, 2016.

Abstract:

Teachers role is numerous and utterly important. A teacher's contribution in an individual's life is long lasting. Job satisfaction always increases the capability, productivity of the employee, which is beneficiary for the institution also. If a teacher is satisfied with his job, he can contribute to the development of the students. On the other hand, dissatisfied teacher can create a negative effect on the teaching-learning process and also in the well being of the pupils. The present study aims to signify the level of job satisfaction among higher secondary school teachers and to find significant difference in job satisfaction with regard to gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction and teaching stream. Findings of the study revealed average level of job satisfaction among all teachers and there is significant towards gender and other category of locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction and teaching stream do not differ towards job satisfaction of higher secondary school teachers.

Introduction:

Teachers are the spine of the society. His role is numerous and utterly important. A teacher's contribution in an individual's life is long lasting. Teaching is one of the noble professions in the world. Almost all the educational commissions and committees have focused on the teacher's role and duties, as well as their working conditions. The Education Commission (1964-66) or The Kothari Commission properly said that of all the different factor which influence the quality of education and its contribution to the national development, the quality competence and character of teachers are undoubtedly the most significant. Nothing is more important than securing a sufficient supply of high quality recruits to the teaching profession providing them with the best of work in which they can be fully effective (Kumar, P. 2014). The Programme of Action (1992) has put forward some guidelines regarding teacher recruitment, job benefits, etc. it stated that, the status of teachers has had a direct bearing on the quality of education and many of the ills of the latter can be ascribed to the indifferent manner in which society has looked upon the teacher and the manner in which many teachers have performed their functions (source: <http://www.teindia.nic.in/Files/Reports/CCR/POA>).

Traditionally teachers enjoyed a higher status in the society and they also enjoyed great respect. But in the last few decades, teacher's position has diminished due to various factors. The teachers in India suffer from neglect, poverty, indifference, insecurity and obviously disrespect. Consequently, teachers lack job satisfaction in their field.

Job Satisfaction:

Job satisfaction is related to a number of psychological and social issues. It depends on various factors too. Its scope is wider than individual's expectations. Due to this job satisfaction is one of the most important research issues in Psychology. The level of job satisfaction depends upon multiple factors like physical condition of the work place, relation among the co-workers, effectiveness of the head of the institutions, working hour, work pressure, administrative duties, students behavior, adjustment ability, gender, remuneration, etc. all these factors are interrelated and cannot be separated from each other. According to job satisfaction and vocational guidance pioneer Robert Hoppock, job satisfaction is any combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances that caused a person truthfully to say "I am satisfied with my job" (Hoppock, R., 1935). Poling also said that (1994), the best predictor of job satisfaction is when the employee's personal values match those of the organization (Poling, R. L., 1990). Locke (1976) defined job satisfaction as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Job_satisfaction).

The satisfaction and dissatisfaction with ones job depends upon the positive or negative evaluation of one's own success or failure in the realization of personal goals and the perceived contribution of job to it (Chutia, M., 2013). Job satisfaction always increases the capability, productivity of the employee, which is beneficiary for the institution also. If a teacher is satisfied with his job he can contribute to the development of the students. On the other hand, dissatisfied teacher can create a negative effect on the teaching-learning process and also in the well being of the pupils.

Need of the Study:

Teaching profession is one of the most challenging one. It is the responsibility of the teacher to develop his students so that they can become individually, socially useful. Not only the academic responsibilities, but teachers have to shoulder many administrative duties in the institution. Compared to other professions, teachers are underpaid in India. If they are to perform their strenuous duty effectively their working conditions should be

made satisfactory. Therefore it is very much significant to study the job satisfaction of higher secondary school teachers.

Method and Sampling Frame:

Considering the objectives of the study the investigator had adopted survey method. The present study concerned with the higher secondary school teachers. The teachers from government, government aided and private schools were taken to constitute the population for the present study. The simple random sampling technique is adopted in the present study. The size of the sample is 300. A personal data sheet was also prepared by the investigator to know about the higher secondary school teacher's gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction and teaching stream.

Tool:

Samples were collected using a personal data sheet prepared by the researcher. Job satisfaction scale by Dr. Brayfield and Rothe (1951) was used for measuring job satisfaction. The scale consisted of 18 items. It was a 5 point (strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, strongly disagree) likert type scale. The scores of all the items were summed up for deriving an individual's job satisfaction score. The score ranges from 18-90. The investigator has calculated the Test-Re-test method to find the reliability of the scale on job satisfaction among higher secondary school teachers and the value of reliability was 0.92.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the level of job satisfaction of higher secondary school teachers.
- ✓ To find out significant difference between female and male higher secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction.
- ✓ To find out significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction.
- ✓ To find out significant difference between type of management of higher secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction.
- ✓ To find out significant difference between medium of instruction of higher secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction.
- ✓ To find out significant difference between teaching stream of higher secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction.

Hypotheses:

- The level of job satisfaction of higher secondary school teachers is high.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between female and male higher secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between type of management of higher secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between medium of instruction of higher secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between teaching stream of higher secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction.

Data Analysis:

Table 1: Level of Job Satisfaction of Higher Secondary School Teachers

Variables	Sample	N	MEAN	SD	Level
Gender	Male	168	63.65	16.16	Average
	Female	132	59.78	16.84	
Locality of School	Rural	128	62.73	16.63	Average
	Urban	172	61.38	16.50	
Type of Management	Government	110	61.76	16.45	Average
	Govt Aided	114	62.04	16.88	
	Private	78	62.11	16.36	
Medium of Instruction	Tamil	118	69.48	16.56	Average
	English	127	63.39	16.05	
	Both	57	61.77	17.69	
Teaching Stream	Science	135	63.22	16.91	Average
	Maths	106	59.95	16.01	
	Arts	59	52.64	16.51	
Entire Sample		300	61.96	16.54	

It was also noticed from the above table 1, that mean score of job satisfaction for entire sample of higher secondary school teachers was secured scores lies between 45.42 to 78.5 (-1σ to +1σ) are classified as

average job satisfaction. So it is found that entire sample of higher secondary school teachers also had an average job satisfaction. Therefore, it is found that the higher secondary school teachers irrespective of their gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction and teaching stream have average level of job satisfaction.

Table 2: Significant Difference between Male and Female Higher Secondary School Teachers with regard to their Job Satisfaction

Gender	N	Mean	SD	"t" Value	LS
Male	168	63.65	16.16	2.026	S
Female	132	59.78	16.84		

It was seen from Table-2, the calculated t-value is 2.026. Which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that male and female higher secondary school teachers differ significantly in their job satisfaction. So there is significant difference between male and female higher secondary school teachers with regard to their job satisfaction.

Table 3: Significant Difference between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary School Teachers with regard to their Job Satisfaction

Locality of School	N	Mean	SD	"t" Value	LS
Rural	128	62.73	16.63	0.699	N S
Urban	172	61.38	16.50		

It was seen from Table-3, the calculated t-value is 0.699. Which is not significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that rural and urban of higher secondary school teachers do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction. So there is no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary school teachers with regard to their job satisfaction.

Table 4: Significant Difference in Job Satisfaction among Higher Secondary School Teachers with regard to their Type of Management

Group	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	'F' Value	LS
Between Groups	6.951	2	3.475	0.013	NS
Within Groups	81870.569	297	275.658		
Total	81877.520	299			

It was seen from Table-4, the calculated F-value is 0.013. Which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. So it is found that there is no significant difference in job satisfaction among higher secondary school teachers with regard to their type of management.

Table 5: Significant Difference in Job Satisfaction among Higher Secondary School Teachers with regard to their Medium of Instruction

Group	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	'F' Value	LS
Between Groups	516.204	2	256.102	0.942	NS
Within Groups	81361.316	297	273.944		
Total	81877.520	299			

It was seen from Table-5, the calculated F-value is 0.942. Which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. So it is found that there is no significant difference in job satisfaction among higher secondary school teachers with regard to their medium of instruction.

Table 6: Significant Difference in Job Satisfaction among Higher Secondary School Teachers with regard to their Teaching Stream

Group	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	'F' Value	LS
Between Groups	668.264	2	334.132	1.222	NS
Within Groups	81209.256	297	273.432		
Total	81877.520	299			

It was seen from Table-6, the calculated F-value is 1.222. Which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. So it is found that there is no significant difference in job satisfaction among higher secondary school teachers with regard to their teaching stream.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ The study revealed that the higher secondary school teachers with regard to their entire sample, gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction and teaching stream have average level of job satisfaction.
- ✓ The study revealed that there was significant difference between female and male higher secondary school teachers with regard to their job satisfaction.
- ✓ The study revealed that there was no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary school teachers with regard to their job satisfaction.
- ✓ The study revealed that there was no significant difference between type of management of higher secondary school teachers with regard to their job satisfaction.

- ✓ The study revealed that there was no significant difference between medium of instruction of higher secondary school teachers with regard to their job satisfaction.
- ✓ The study revealed that there was no significant difference between medium teaching stream of higher secondary school teachers with regard to their job satisfaction.

Conclusion:

The present study showed that higher secondary school teachers had average job satisfaction level. But the “others” category teachers were dissatisfied with their job. Proper pay scale, job security, work environment should be introduced for them. Teaching is a unique profession that leads to betterment of the society, making of good human being and responsible citizens. Teachers have to perform this strenuous duty with utmost care and expertise. Therefore, their personal satisfaction regarding the job and other factors related to it is very important.

Suggestions and Scope of Further Research:

On the basis of this study the investigator forwards some suggestive measures to attain higher job satisfaction among all groups of teachers. All infrastructural facilities, administration and management should be improved. Teachers should be recruited through a proper channel and effective policy. Teacher- student ratio should be in proper shape. Pay scale, working environment, promotional benefits, after service benefits must be upgraded. Part time and contractual teachers should get job security as well as proper pay scale according to their qualification and work load. The same study could be carried out on teachers from different streams, both in school and college level. Comparative studies could be made to find out the satisfaction level of regular and distance course teachers also.

References:

1. Best John, W., & Khan, James, V. (2008) Research in Education, Tenth Edition, New Delhi. Prentice Hall of India Private Ltd.
2. Chutia, M., (2013). ‘Is job satisfaction U-shaped in age?’, Journal of Occupational and Organisational Psychology, 69, 1996, pp. 57-81.
3. Garrett, Henry & Wood Worth, R.S. (2008). Statistics in Psychology and Education, Surjeet Publications Ltd, New Delhi.
4. Guilford. J.P (1956) “Fundamental Statistics in Psychology and Education” New York, Mc Graw Hill Book Company Inc.
5. Hoppock, R. (2005). Job satisfaction. New York: Harper and Brothers, p.47.
6. Kumar P (2013) Development of job satisfaction scale for health care providers. India: NIHFV Unpublished.
7. Locke, E.A., ‘The Nature and Causes of Job Satisfaction’. In Dunnette, M.P. (Ed.) Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology, Chicago: Rand McNally, 1976, pp. 1297-1350.
8. Lokesh Koul (1990) Methodology of Educational Research (2nd Ed) New Delhi, Vikas Publishing house Pvt. Ltd.,
9. Poling, R. L. (1990). Factors associated with job satisfaction of faculty members at a land-grant university. Summary of Research in Extension, 5, 143.
10. www.ingentacon-ect.com/content/
11. www.ingentaselect.com/bps/activate.htm
12. www.ipat.com
13. www.journals.cambridge.org
14. www.nature.com
15. www.sciencedirect.com
16. www.somaticinkblots.com
17. www.thomsonnights.com
18. www.wadsworth.com
19. www.helpageindia.org
20. www.apa.org/books